

“Osseointegration” a histological representation of bone-implant interface.

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Abstract:

A direct structural and functional association between organized, living bone and the surface of the load-bearing implant is referred to as osseointegration. An implant is considered as osseointegrated when there is no incremental relative movement between the implant and the bone with which it has direct contact. The aim of this review is to assess the basic science work done on the concept of osseointegration biology, and to discuss the factors that may affect osseous healing around an implant.

Keywords: Osseointegration, bone-implant interface, bone, dental implant, implant surface.

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Introduction

Modern dentistry aims to restore normal function, speech, aesthetics, contour, comfort, and wellbeing to patients. As a result of continued research, diagnostic aids, structured approach in treatment planning, design of implant, materials and techniques, Predictable progress is now a reality for the recovery of many complex clinical situations. Treatment options have evolved from acrylic dentures to metal framework, removable partial dentures to fixed partial dentures. Recently dental implant has joined the armamentarium & its success is based on principle osseointegration¹.

The term osseointegration (from latin osseum “bone” and integrate “to make whole”) was coined by Branemark in 1977. Osseointegration is defined as a direct attachment or connection of osseous tissue to an inert, alloplastic material without intervening fibrous connective tissue.² The establishment and maintenance of osseointegration is dependent on an understanding of the tissue's healing, repair, and remodeling capacities. A basic requirement for establishing true and lasting

tissue integration of a nonbiologic prosthesis with minimal risk of adverse local or general tissue reactions consists of a detailed understanding of the response behavior of highly differentiated hard and soft tissues to surgical preparation of recipient site, and installation of the prosthesis, as well as the long-term tissue adaptation to functional demands on the anchorage unit³.

Osseointegration is similar to direct fracture healing in that the fragment ends become joined by bone without the formation of intermediate fibrous tissue or fibrocartilage. Osseointegration is a process that connects bone to an implant surface, rather than bone to bone. Thus, the material plays a critical role in achieving union. Albrektsson et al first referred some important factors which determine the success of osseointegration. These are implant biocompatibility, patients systemic condition, design characteristics, state of the host bed, implant surface, surgical technique and the implant loading conditions⁴. The aim of this review is to discuss basic science work on the definition of osseointegration biology and to determine and evaluate the factors that go into achieving

effective osseous healing around an implant in a reasonable amount of time given current knowledge

Biology of bone

Bone is classified as either Compact bone (Cortical bone) or Spongy bone (Cancellous bone). Compact bone is made up of lamellae, or cell layers, and a matrix composed of inorganic and organic components. The cells that are present are known as osteocytes. They are located in lacunae and have cell processes that allow nutrients to diffuse through small channels called canaliculi. The matrix component or osteoid is approximately 40% by weight and consists of Type I collagen, glycosaminoglycans and the adhesive protein, osteonectin. The inorganic component, which is approximately 40% by weight, consists of hydroxyapatite crystals. Compact bone has outer circumferential lamellae, inner circumferential lamellae, haversian lamellae, and interstitial lamellae which account for hardness and density. It is covered by periosteum and is tightly attached to the bone surface by Sharpey's fibres and serves as protection for the bone. Spongy bone has a three-dimensional network called bone trabeculae inside compact bone. As compared to compact bone, spongy bone construction is cavernous and less dense, resulting in lower hardness. The arrangement of bone trabeculae provides a large surface area for a large number of osteoblasts and osteoclasts.³

Mechanism of osseointegration

- 1) Tissue response to osseointegration
- 2) Peri-implant Osteogenesis
- 3) Peri- implant Remodeling

Tissue response to osseointegration

A bioactive substance is thought to induce a favourable tissue reaction by forming chemical bonds with tissue components (hydroxyapatite) or by promoting cellular

activities involved in the formation of the bone matrix.⁴ Bone healing around an implant involves a series of cellular and extracellular biological events. The first biological component to come into contact with an endosseous implant is blood. Blood cells, such as red blood cells and platelets, as well as inflammatory cells, such as polymorphonuclear granulocytes and monocytes, emigrate from post-capillary sites and move into the tissue surrounding the implant. These cells get entrapped at the bone-implant interface, causing cytokines to activate and release and regulates the growth and differentiation factors. Platelet when comes into contact with the synthetic surface, they release serotonin and histamine causing further platelet aggregation and thrombosis at the ruptured blood vessels. Initial reactions of blood cells with the implant influence clot formation as soon as blood contacts proteins or a foreign material causing blood coagulation. This blood clot permeates the wound space forming a provisional fibrin matrix and get adheres to the implant surface. The formed fibrin matrix acts as a scaffold (Osseosynthesis) for the migration of osteogenic cells and eventual differentiation (Osteoinduction) of these cells in the healing compartment^{5,6}.

Peri-implant osteogenesis (De novo bone formation)

Peri-implant osteogenesis can be in distance and in contact from the host bone which was first describe by Osborn and Newesley in 1980 & referred to the general relationship between bone formation & implant surface. In distance osteogenesis refers to newly formed bone that develops from healing bone towards the implant. Contrast to that, In contact osteogenesis refers to newly formed bone on the implant surface, since no bone was present on the surface of the implant upon implantation^{1,5}. This matrix is a 0.5 mm thick, early developed calcified afibrillar

layer rich in calcium, phosphorus, osteopontin, and bone sialoprotein.

Metabolism of the local inflammatory cells, fibroblast, progenitor cells and other local cells creates an area of relative hypoxia in the wound area which triggers the local mesenchymal cells or the osteogenic cells to differentiate into fibroblast, osteoblast and chondroblast. An extracellular matrix is laid down by these cells & eventually a fibrocartilaginous callus formed. Initial immature bone is called the woven bone and the trabecular bone is formed, which shows a very active wide surface area, contiguous with marrow spaces rich in vascular and mesenchymal cells. Its physical architecture includes arches and bridges which offers as a biological scaffold for cell attachment and bone deposition that is biologic fixation. Marrow tissues contains a very rich vasculature supports mononuclear precursors of osteoclasts so trabecular bone remodel faster than cortical bone. This woven bone & the trabecular bone progressively matures, remodeled and substituted by lamellar bone that may reach high degree of mineralization^{5,6,7}.

The newly formed bone was laid down on the reabsorbed surface of the old bone after the osteoclastic activity. The host bone chips between the implant and the host bone cavity presumably occur from the surgical bur preparation of implant insertion. These are enveloped in a newly formed peri-implant trabecular bone, and seem to be involved in trabecular formation during the first week i.e in the primary stability of the implant. Therefore, it may be useful in clinical practice not washing with saline solution or aspirating the bone cavity before or during the implant insertion⁵.

Peri-implant remodeling (Adaptation of bone mass to load)

Bone remodeling characterizes the last stage of osseointegration which is of particularly

critical importance in the long term stability of the implant.^{1,4} When the prosthesis has been connected to the abutments, the jawbone around the anchoring element will continue to remodel during several years until a "steady state" has been reached. This morphological remodeling is due to adaptation to stress and mechanical loading. Due to the surgical trauma at fixture insertion and the gradual adaptation to the load, some marginal bone is lost during the remodeling phase, whereas once the steady state has been reached, negligible bone resorption takes place as evaluated at yearly radiographic examinations using computerized periodic identical radiography (Figure 1).^[3,5]

New bone is created near to the immobile resting implant during the healing process. As masticatory forces are applied to the implant, the newly formed bone remodels in accordance with the magnitude, direction, and frequency of the applied force. After about 18 months steady state is achieved, which means that there is a balance between the forces acting on the implant and the remodeling capacities of the anchoring bone. The hatched area at the top of the diagram illustrates the reduction in height of the anchoring bone which occurs during healing and remodeling phase.³

In cortical as well as in cancellous bone, remodeling occurs in discrete units, often called as bone multicellular unit as proposed by frost. Remodeling starts with osteoclastic resorption, followed by lamellar bone deposition. In cortical bone, a bone multicellular unit consists of a squad of osteoclasts that form a sort of drill head & produce a cylindrical canal with a diameter equal to an osteon that is 150-200 um. These osteoclasts advance with the speed of about 50 um/day & is followed by a vascular loop, accompanied by perivascular osteoprogenitor cells. About 100um behind the osteoclast, the first osteoblast line up upon the wall of the resorption canal and begin to deposit

concentric layer of lamellar bone. After 2-4 months, the new osteon is completed. These new osteons circle around the implant with their long axes parallel to the implant surfaces and perpendicular to the long axis of the implant. In the trabecular surface, remodeling starts with an accumulation of osteoclasts that produce an erosion cavity. Osteoblasts emerge a few days later and fill the eroded space with new lamellar bone, also known as lamellar packet or simply packet.^{5,8}

Factors affecting or enhancing Osseointegration

1. Biocompatibility

The dental implant biomaterials are devices that extend from the bone to the oral cavity across the protective epithelial zones. Hence these materials should have the property of biocompatibility¹. Biomaterials are capable of existing in harmony with the surrounding biologic environment². Titanium seemed to have better mechanical and surface characteristics for implantation in a biologic environment.³ Pure titanium (Ti) is widely used as an implant material as it is highly biocompatible, it has good resistance to corrosion, and no toxicity on macrophages or fibroblasts, lack of inflammatory response in peri-implant tissue and its surface is composed of an oxide layer and has the ability to repair itself by reoxidation when damaged⁴. Other materials as an alternative to titanium include tantalum, aluminum, niobium, nickel, zirconia & hafnium. Porous coating of an implant inhibits bone ingrowth, the properties of porous tantalum include high volumetric porosity, low modulus of elasticity, high frictional characteristics and excellent biocompatibility. In vitro studies have shown osteoblast growth and differentiation related to porous tantalum implants.⁵

1) Stability

The goal in implant placement is to achieve primary implant stability⁶. Two terms such as primary and secondary implant stability are related to implant therapy. Primary stability is associated with the mechanical engagement of an implant with the surrounding bone, whereas secondary stability offers biological stability through bone regeneration and remodeling. A secure primary stability is positively associated with secondary stability. The success of this adaptation, however, depends on several factors, including the density and dimension of the bone surrounding the implant, the implant design, and surgical technique used (Figure 2).

There are certain methods to measure the clinical stability of an implant, namely the periotest (PT) (Figure 3) and the resonance frequency analysis (RFA) measurement using osstell device (Figure 4 and 5). Periotest was introduced by Schulte, it quantifies the mobility of an implant by measuring the reaction of the peri-implant tissues to a defined impact load. Periotest® uses an electro-magnetically driven and electronically controlled tapping metallic rod in a handpiece. Periotest value range from -8 (low mobility) to +50 (high mobility). It can measure the bone density at the time of implant placement and postsurgical placement of the implant.^{9,10}

The RFA device measures the resonance frequency of a transducer attached to the implant body or abutment by screw, which is stimulated by different frequencies. This instrument has a graphic display panel showing the implant stability quotient (ISQ) values, which indicate the firmness at the implant-tissue interface. ISQ values greater than 65 have been regarded as most favorable for implant stability, whereas ISQ values below 45 indicate a poor primary stability.^{9,10}

2) *Bone quality*

The quality and quantity of the bone available are highly interrelated with all the factors mentioned above and below like surgical techniques, implant design, materials and surface properties. Clinical reports show that oral implants placed in mandible have higher survival rates than those placed in maxilla. Bone quality is considered here to be the main cause where the mandible has the superiority in this matter. The most common classification is that suggested by Lekholm and Zarb for types of bone quality shown in (Figure 6). Type I, the entire bone is composed of very thick cortical bone. Type II, thick layer of cortical bone surrounds a core of dense trabecular bone. Type III, thin layer of cortical bone surrounds a core of trabecular bone of good strength. Type IV, very thin layer of cortical bone with low density trabecular bone of poor strength.

Placing implants in type 1 to type 3 bone leads to good clinical outcomes whereas type 4 is linked with lower success rates. Stability of implants in type 4 bone can be increased by manual condensation of bone around the implants. The ratio between cortical and trabecular bone in addition to bone volume and density has a prevailing influence on implant success. Trabecular bone is filled with bone marrow, source of osteoblast and osteoclasts, and has therefore higher turnover than cortical bone. Trabecular is high in mandible than maxilla, anterior than posterior in males than females. Many studies have shown the required bone volume when planning an oral implant where at least 10mm and 6mm in height and 5mm and 6mm in width for maxilla and mandible are required for successful placement and osseointegration. Cellular characteristics of bone quality include monocytes/macrophages, mesenchymal progenitor cell, fibroblasts, osteoclasts and cells associated with angiogenesis may contribute to the success of local process of

osseointegration. Bone quality can also be determined by CT scans, cutting torque and resonance frequency assessment of implant stability that have a major role in success of osseointegration^{11,12}

3) *Design of dental implant*

The implant design is a vital for attaining an influence in osseointegration. Originally implants were fabricated in parallel design, however they were not appropriate for most application. Implant design features are one of the most fundamental element that have an effect in implants ability to sustain loading during and after osseointegration.⁹ Its divided into two major categories macrodesign and microdesign. Macrodesign includes implant body shape and thread design] e.g. thread geometry, face angle, thread pitch, thread depth and thread helix angle¹³.

Different implant body designs available in implant dentistry. They may be categorized as cylinder type, screw type, press fit, or a combination of features. Originally parallel implants were introduced; however they were not appropriate for most application. Later tapered implants were introduced, the hypothesis behind using this implant was to provide a degree of compression in cortical bone in implant site with inadequate bone but the Lesser surface area of tapered implant increases the amount of stress at crestal portion^{9,13}. Cylindrical wide body implant increase the risk of labial bone perforation due to presence of buccal concavities, whereas the decrease in diameter of tapered implant towards the apical region accommodates labial concavities ensuring the success of the treatment^{9,12}. The design parameters primarily affects biomechanical load distribution in the bone tissue, to optimize the implant-supported prosthesis function^{12,13}. The most important factor that influences the load transfer at the bone-implant interface are length, diameter and

body/thread shape¹⁴. In type I and II bone, length and diameter do not seem to be significant factor for implant success but in type III and IV, large diameter implant is needed as it will decrease the peak values and stress distribution will be more homogenous at cancellous bone-implant interface. Whereas Body geometry must rely on a microscopic retention system such as roughening or coating (Acid etch, mechanical etch, or coating such as titanium plasma spray or hydroxyapatite) for the initial loading period. Bone is weaker when loaded under an angled force. The greater the angle of load the greater the stresses to implant-bone interface. Therefore, under ideal condition, the implant body long axis should be perpendicular to the curve of Wilson and curve of spee to apply along axis load to the implant during occlusal load in centric occlusion^{13, 14}. Threads are designed to maximize the initial contact which enhances surface area and facilitate dissipation of load at the bone implant interface. Misch and colleagues stated that deeper the threads, the wider the surface area of the implant. If bone quality and quantity are optimal, then they may compensate for implant design inadequacy^{9,13,14}.

4) Implant surface

The starting point for implant surface design is machinable implant surfaces. They were used for decades according to traditional protocols, which took several months for osseointegration. It has been shown that altering the topographic pattern of a surface enhances not only the bone-implant communication, but also the biomechanical interaction of that interface during the early stages of implantation. Rough surfaces have been widely used in oral implantology, and have largely replaced implants with machined surfaces in clinical applications.

Various methods have been developed in order to create a rough surface and improve the osseointegration of titanium dental implants. These methods use titanium plasma-spraying, blasting with ceramic particles, acid-etching and anodization.¹⁵

a. Titanium plasma-spraying

This process entails injecting titanium powders into a high-temperature plasma torch. The titanium particles are projected onto the implant surface, where they condense and fuse together to form a titanium plasma sprayed (TPS) coating with an average roughness of around 7 μm . This technique significantly improves the surface area of the implants. TPS processing is one of the methods that further increase the surface roughness profile and consequently the surface area. Because of these features, it is recommended for use in areas where bone density is limited¹⁶. However, when the implant surface is exposed to oral fluids, the rise in surface area that constitutes an effective increase in osseointegration area provides spaces greater than 50 μm , which promotes pathogen migration¹⁵.

b. Blasting with ceramic particles/Acid-etching

Surface acid-etching and grit-blasting/acid-etching are very diffuse methods to obtain rough implant surfaces. A great part of the commercially available grit-blasted implant surfaces are subsequently acid-etched. Generally, the grit-blasting procedure is performed by propulsion of particles of different sizes of silica (sand), alumina, titanium oxide or CaP for example. The most commonly used acid-etching agents are hydrofluoric, nitric, sulfuric acids and combinations. An example of this group of surfaces was investigated by Sammons et al.¹⁷, evidencing a Ra value of 2.75 μm and irregular micropores with approximately 3-5

μm in diameter and 2-3 μm in depth. Even smaller micropores are located within these micropores. Recently, it was seen that changing the sterilization and storage method of an original sand-blasted/acid-etched surface is another possible way to modify implant surface. In other words, the new surface is rinsed under nitrogen protection to prevent exposure to air and then stored in a sealed tube containing an isotonic saline solution¹⁸. This method increased the surface wettability of the new surface as compared to the original one in a statistically significant level by obtaining the hydroxylation of titanium oxides without altering the surface topography¹⁹. These results suggest that a chemical modification on a microstructured implant surface may interfere in the biomechanical and bone apposition properties at early phases after implantation.

c. Electrochemical anodization

Electrochemical anodization is another process that has been shown to increase surface microtexture and alter surface chemistry. The thickening of the titanium oxide layer is caused by the combination of potentiostatic or galvanostatic anodization of titanium in strong acids at high current density or potential. As compared to machined surfaces, anodized surfaces interact positively with bone reaction, yielding higher values for biomechanical and histomorphometric tests^{20,21}.

d. CaP and HA coatings

Up to now, plasma-spraying remains as the most widely used commercial CaP implant surface coating. CaP ceramics are thought to have bioactive properties, which include a heavy chemical bonding between the materials and the surrounding bone. As compared to those without CaP coatings, substrates with CaP coatings are expected to

have faster biological fixation between implant and bone tissue¹⁵. However, the plasma-spraying process, which involves injecting Hydroxyapatite HA ceramic particles into a high-temperature plasma torch and projecting them onto the titanium surface, has also been connected to some drawback²². Additionally, the transmucosal zone of plasma sprayed HA implants represents a challenge²³ in terms of periimplantitis infection. Based on these reasons, the clinical use of the plasma sprayed HA implants decreased, but the osteoconductive property of this bioactive ceramic coating remains as a factor that may contribute to additional bone attachment in areas of poor quality or quantity of bone. Changes in surface roughness at the nanoscale level tend to have a significant impact on the host response at both the cellular and tissue levels, according to a new trend. In comparison to the plasma sprayed HA technique, methods such as sol-gel deposition, electrophoretic deposition, and discrete crystalline deposition were designed to achieve significantly thinner coating thicknesses.

The study conducted by Rodrigo A. da Silva²⁴ to better understand the biological behavior of osteoblasts grown on nanosized crystalline hydroxyapatite coating HAnano® surface, the set of data was compared with SLActive®, a hydrophilic sandblasted titanium surface. Osteoblasts were seeded on both surfaces for 72 hours to determine cell adhesion, viability, and a set of genes encoding proteins involved in adhesion, proliferation, and differentiation. The obtained data shows HAnano® displays an interesting substrate to support cell adhesion with typical spread morphologic cells, while SLActive®-adhering cells presented fusiform morphology. Our data shows that the cellular adhesion mechanism was accompanied with upexpression of *integrin*

β1, *Fak*, and *Src*, favoring the assembling of focal adhesion platforms and coupling cell cycle progression (upmodulating of *Cdk2*, *Cdk4*, and *Cdk6* genes) in response to HAnano®. Additionally, both bioactive surfaces promoted osteoblast differentiation stimulus, by activating *Runx2*, *Osterix*, and *Alp* genes. Although both surfaces promoted *Rankl* gene expression, *Opg* gene expression was higher in SLActive® and this difference reflected on the *Rankl/Opg* ratio. Finally, *Caspase1* gene was significantly upmodulated in response to HAnano® and it suggests an involvement of the inflammasome complex. Collectively, this study provides enough evidences to support that the nanohydroxyapatite-coated surface provides the necessary microenvironment to drive osteoblast performance on dental implants and these stages of osteogenesis are expected during the early stages of osseointegration.

The main biological mechanisms triggered by the HAnano-modified surface in osteoblast responses is depicted in (Figure 7). When in contact with the surface, osteoblast upmodulates the activity of a set of genes related with cell adhesion at early 3 and 24 hours and further compromises the expression of genes related with osteoblast differentiation. Importantly, calcium and phosphate ions are hypothesized to be released as described within current literature which triggers signaling pathway upstream activating osteoblast proliferation and differentiation. Altogether, these biological stages of osteoblast biology culminate on osteogenesis process and are expected being recapitulated during osseointegration of dental implants.

Conclusion

The use of tissue-integrated implants to replace missing natural teeth represents a significant advancement in clinical treatment. Over the last four decades, implant prosthesis

knowledge has progressed from experimental laboratory phases to evidence-based clinical practice. Nanotechnology tends to be the way of the future, which it will inevitably become as genetic engineering progresses.

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Figures

Figure 1

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Figure 4

Figure 5

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Figure 7

